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A Comparison Study on Lok Sabha and Rajya Sabha of India

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Abstract:

The maximum strength of 552 members, including representatives of the people and a few nominated members. Currently, the house has 543 seats which are filled by the election of up to 543 elected members. Between 1952 and 2020, two additional members of the Anglo-Indian community were also nominated by the President of India on the advice of the Government of India, which was abolished in January 2020 by the 104th Constitutional Amendment Act, 2019. Understanding the Difference between Lok Sabha and Rajya Sabha is essential to grasp the nuances of the Indian legislative process.

Introduction:

The Lok Sabha, also known as the House of the People, is directly elected by the citizens of India and serves as the lower house of Parliament. It has a maximum strength of 552 members, including representatives of the people and a few nominated members.

The maximum membership of the House allotted by the Constitution of India is 552 but it was initially, in 1950, is 500. Currently, the house has 543 seats which are filled by the election of up to 543 elected members.

Between 1952 and 2020, two additional members of the Anglo-Indian community were also nominated by the President of India on the advice of the Government of India, which was abolished in January 2020 by the 104th Constitutional Amendment Act, 2019. The new parliament has a seating capacity of 888 for Lok Sabha.

The Rajya Sabha, or the Council of States, is the upper house and has a maximum strength of 250 members, who are elected by the elected members of State Legislative Assemblies and by the members of the Electoral College for Union Territories, with some members nominated by the President for their expertise in specific fields.

Lok Sabha and Rajya Sabha:

The Lok Sabha is responsible for making and passing laws and plays a significant role in the financial matters as all money bills can only be introduced in the Lok Sabha. The Rajya Sabha reviews, suggests amendments, and provides a check on the legislation passed by the Lok Sabha. Understanding the Difference between Lok Sabha and Rajya Sabha is essential to grasp the nuances of the Indian legislative process. Here some of the major distinctions between both the houses were discussed below:

➤ Constitutional Provision:

Article 81 deals with the composition of the House of People and whereas Rajya sabha Article 80 is associated with the composition of the Council of States.

➤ Tenure Period:

The tenure of the Lok Sabha is normally 5 years and whereas Rajya Sabha is a permanent house of parliament with no fixed tenure.

➤ Election for Membership:

The members of the Lok Sabha are elected through the voting process with

the involvement of the common people. Whereas, the member's of the Rajya Sabha are elected by the representatives of state legislative assemblies of states and union territories.

➤ **Election Principle:**

Universal Adult Franchise is applied for the Lok Sabha election. And about Rajya Sabha the proportional representation by means of single transferable votes is applied for the Rajya Sabha election.

➤ **Minimum Age:**

To be an MP (Member of Parliament) of the Lok Sabha, one has to be at least 25 years of age. And to be a Member of Parliament of the Rajya Sabha, one has to be at least 30 years of age.

➤ **House Representative:**

The business of Lok Sabha is conducted by the speaker of Lok Sabha. And the business of Rajya Sabha is conducted by the Vice-President as the chairman of Rajya Sabha.

➤ **Role:**

Lok Sabha has a greater role in legislation and passing money bills as compared to the Rajya Sabha. And Rajya Sabha has exclusive rights and powers to make laws on state lists and create new all-India services.

➤ **Strength:**

The strength of the Lok Sabha ranges from 500 to 552. Presently, there are 543 seats. And the strength of the Rajya Sabha ranges from 200 to 250. Currently, there are 245 seats.

➤ **Exceptional power:**

When Lok Sabha is dissolved before or after the declaration of a National Emergency, the Rajya Sabha becomes the sole Parliament. It cannot be dissolved. This is a limitation on the Lok Sabha. But there is a possibility that the president can exceed the term to not more than 1 year under the proclamation of emergency and the same would be lowered down to six-month if the said proclamation ceases to operate.

Conclusion:

In simply say's the Lok Sabha is more powerful house than the Rajya Sabha in almost all matters. Even in those matters in which the Constitution has placed both Houses on an equal footing.

Whereas, the Lok Sabha has more influence due to its greater numerical strength. This is typical of parliamentary democracies, many of which have a lower house that is more powerful than the upper house.

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